

deficiency was not related to grain length/fineness or biomass produced per plant (see table). Contrary to the belief that B deficiency hampers grain setting more than vegetative growth (Rerkasem and Jamod 1997), the magnitude of straw biomass reduction was greater than grain yield reduction in Super Basmati, DR83, Basmati 385, and Pakhal.

Rice cultivars differed significantly in B uptake when grown under identical environmental conditions. For example, Basmati 6129 was 2.6 times more efficient in using B from B-deficient soil than Pakhal ($P < 0.05$; see table). Despite its higher B use efficiency, however, Basmati 6129 was more susceptible to B deficiency than Pakhal (see table). Fertilizer B recovery is the fraction of applied B taken up in aboveground plant parts, while agronomic efficiency refers to extra grain yield over

the control yield per unit of applied B. Boron-efficient and -inefficient rice genotypes were distinguishable by B concentration in their B-deficient plant tissues, B uptake, fertilizer B recovery, and agronomic efficiency (see table).

Basmati is famous for its aroma and long, fine grains. As Super Basmati, a premier basmati cultivar in Pakistan, was more sensitive to B deficiency than other basmati varieties, the situation is rather alarming because of widespread low soil B in Pakistan (NFDC 1998) and elsewhere (Shorrocks 1997). Boron efficiency is believed to be a single gene-controlled trait. Therefore, tailoring or selecting plant genotypes for B-deficient soils might be more practical than changing the soil to fit the plant. Genetic manipulation, through an efficient molecular approach, could help transfer the B-efficient trait of

Basmati 370 or IR6 into currently popular fine aromatic varieties such as Super Basmati.

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Effect of mixing black clay soil and organic amendment on properties of coarse-textured soil and rice yield

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In Tamil Nadu, rice is grown on coarse-textured soils across a significant area with marginal yields. To improve soil, water, and nutrient retention and to enhance rice yields, a field experiment was conducted during the wet seasons of 1996-97 and 1997-98 (October-January), with each season trial done in one of two adjacent fields. Treatments used were different incorporation levels of black clay soil (0, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 t ha⁻¹), with or without 25 t raw coir pith ha⁻¹, replicated thrice in a randomized block design. The black clay soil and coir pith were mixed with the puddled soil up to 20 cm depth by trampling and leveling before transplanting. At the beginning of the experiment, soil in control plots had comparable properties such as contents of clay, silt, organic carbon, total N, P, K, Ca, and Mg, available N, P, K, and exchangeable Ca and Mg, electrical conductivity (EC), pH, and cation ex-

change capacity (CEC) as the soil in the rest of the field. Rice varieties IR60 and ADT36 (parentage: local variety, Triveni/IR20) were grown in the first and second croppings, respectively. Grain and straw yield were recorded. Neither field supported any crop other than the wet-season rice crop under study. The soil was coarse-textured throughout the solum of 2 m and was classified as a coarse loamy, kaolinitic, nonacid, isomegathemic Typic Ustipsamment.

Postharvest soil samples (0–20 cm) were analyzed for particle size (International Pipette), organic carbon (chromic acid), EC and pH (saturation paste extract), NH₄OAc-CEC, Kjeldahl-total N, Pemberton-total P, total K (Stanford and English), total Ca and Mg (Versonate), available N (KMnO₄), Olsen P, and NH₄OAc-extractable K, Ca, and Mg.

All soil properties were influenced

by treatments (see table). For incremental amendments of 20 t black clay soil ha⁻¹, there was progressive improvement in most of the parameters, which might have enhanced crop yield. Addition of coir pith alone or in combination with black clay soil helped boost levels of available N, K, and organic carbon. Reduction in total soil K, Ca, and Mg due to coir pith addition suggested soil dissolution by organic acids produced during decomposition of coir pith, which might have promoted increased nutrient availability to the crop. The significant increase in CEC of sandy soil due to the addition of black clay soil may have enhanced nutrient retention and minimized leaching of nutrients, as low CEC can constrain crop performance in coarse-textured soils.

Addition of coir pith alone to sandy soil markedly decreased soil pH, indicating the acidifying effect of organic acid pro-

Effect of mixing black clay soil and organic amendment on sandy soil properties^a at postharvest and yields of rice crop.

Treatment	Clay (%)	Silt (%)	Organic carbon (%)	EC (dS m ⁻¹)	pH	Available (%)			Exch. cations (c mole [p ⁻¹] kg ⁻¹)			CEC (c mole [p ⁻¹] kg ⁻¹)	Total (%)			Yield (t ha ⁻¹)				
						N	P	K	Ca ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺	N		P	K	Ca	Mg	1996-97 IR60		1997-98 ADT36	
																	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Control	14.4	12.3	0.15	0.10	7.4	0.009	0.0003	0.011	1.4	0.8	2.2	0.003	0.10	0.46	0.27	2.3	4.2	2.6	4.1	
20 t black clay soil ha ⁻¹	15.5	13.1	0.26	0.25	7.9	0.011	0.0004	0.013	2.2	1.3	3.3	0.006	0.13	0.57	0.36	2.4	4.6	3.0	4.4	
20 t black clay soil + 25 t coir pith ha ⁻¹	15.7	13.1	0.48	0.12	7.6	0.011	0.0004	0.013	2.1	1.2	4.3	0.005	0.12	0.50	0.34	2.5	4.7	3.1	4.4	
40 t black clay soil ha ⁻¹	16.8	13.9	0.37	0.19	8.2	0.012	0.0005	0.014	3.7	2.1	5.3	0.008	0.16	0.68	0.49	2.6	5.1	3.5	4.7	
40 t black clay soil ha ⁻¹ + 25 t coir pith ha ⁻¹	17.0	13.7	0.53	0.16	7.9	0.013	0.0005	0.015	3.1	1.9	6.3	0.007	0.15	0.62	0.44	2.7	5.2	3.7	4.8	
60 t black clay soil ha ⁻¹	18.0	14.5	0.46	0.20	8.3	0.014	0.0005	0.016	4.5	3.1	7.5	0.009	0.18	0.79	0.59	2.8	5.5	4.0	5.1	
60 t black clay soil + 25 t coir pith ha ⁻¹	18.2	14.3	0.60	0.16	8.1	0.015	0.0006	0.017	4.2	2.9	8.2	0.008	0.17	0.70	0.52	2.9	5.7	4.1	5.1	
80 t black clay soil ha ⁻¹	19.2	15.7	0.54	0.23	8.5	0.015	0.0006	0.017	6.7	3.7	9.4	0.012	0.22	0.88	0.73	3.0	5.8	4.4	5.4	
80 t black clay soil + 25 t coir pith ha ⁻¹	19.4	15.4	0.72	0.19	8.2	0.016	0.0006	0.018	6.4	3.6	10.2	0.010	0.20	0.81	0.70	3.2	6.0	4.6	5.4	
100 t black clay soil ha ⁻¹	20.5	16.5	0.65	0.26	8.6	0.017	0.0007	0.018	7.5	4.4	11.4	0.014	0.23	0.95	0.82	3.3	6.2	5.0	5.6	
100 t black clay soil + 25 t coir pith ha ⁻¹	20.8	16.4	0.73	0.21	8.4	0.017	0.0007	0.019	7.4	4.2	12.1	0.013	0.21	0.89	0.78	3.8	6.8	5.3	6.0	
25 t coir pith ha ⁻¹	14.3	11.6	0.36	0.07	6.7	0.009	0.0004	0.013	1.2	0.6	2.9	0.002	0.10	0.38	0.19	2.4	4.3	2.9	4.2	
SED	0.1	0.1	0.01	0.00	0.1	1.3 x 10 ⁻⁴	1.3 x 10 ⁻⁶	1.3 x 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.001	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.027	0.036	0.033	0.068	
LSD (0.01)	0.2	0.4	0.01	0.02	0.1	3.1 x 10 ⁻⁴	9.3 x 10 ⁻⁶	4.4 x 10 ⁻⁴	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.004	0.00	0.02	0.07	0.076	0.10	0.099	0.193	

^aBecause soil properties of the experimental fields were similar in both seasons, only data pertaining to 1997-98 are presented along with yields of both seasons' experiments. EC = electrical conductivity, SED = standard error of difference, LSD = least significant difference.

duced upon decomposition. Therefore, it is advisable to add coir pith with a pH-buffering material such as black clay soil to slow down acidification.

The treatments significantly influenced yields of grain and straw in both cropping periods. Treatments with black clay soil had the greater benefit, probably due to the integrated effect of all improved soil properties discussed earlier. Grain and straw yields of ADT36 were higher during the 1997-98 wet season than those of IR60 in the previous wet season. The harvest index of ADT36 increased incrementally with the addition of black clay soil from 0.39 to 0.47, but it scarcely responded to the addition of coir pith (data not shown). The harvest index of IR60 did not respond to either treatment.

In summary, adding 100 t of black clay ha⁻¹ alone during the first year and 25 t of raw coir pith ha⁻¹ once every year may enhance the productivity of rice grown on sandy soil. An economic analysis showed that if black clay soil and coir pith are available within 10 km of the experimental field, their application would be profitable proportionate to the level of black clay soil added (data not shown). The highest net profit was US\$297.53 ha⁻¹ (US\$1 = Indian Rs 43) under the treatment of 100 t black clay soil and 25 t coir pith ha⁻¹, and the lowest was under the control plot with US\$57.02 ha⁻¹. These research results would be applicable wherever black clay soil and coir pith treatments are possible.

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